

EVALUATING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS PROJECTS

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Annotation: The influence of foreign investments, especially Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), on the global economy is profound, impacting productivity, employment levels, and innovation. This study investigates the economic efficiency of foreign investments by analyzing their returns against various costs, including social, environmental, and economic factors. By employing quantitative data and case studies from multiple regions, the research identifies critical elements that affect efficiency and suggests strategies for optimizing the outcomes of foreign investments. The results demonstrate that well-structured policy frameworks and strong governance are vital for improving economic efficiency, while challenges like misaligned priorities and limited local capacities can obstruct this process.

Keywords: regional economy, foreign investment, foreign direct investment (FDI), economic development, payback period, net present value, sustainable development.

Enhancing investments in the national economy stands as one of the most effective strategies to foster overall economic growth and facilitate structural reforms, thereby achieving stable growth rates. This is especially pertinent during the current phase of development for Lithuania and other European Union Member States that continue to feel the repercussions of the global economic crisis. The effectiveness of investments is significantly influenced by the meticulous preparation of investment projects. Sustained value creation for a company can only be guaranteed through a robust investment project that includes a comprehensive analysis of all foundational assumptions, accurate projections of expected cash flows, and a thorough evaluation of associated risks.

Making investment decisions presents a significant challenge for any investor or business entity, with the primary objective being the enhancement of the investor's wealth and the increase in the enterprise's value. Key factors influencing this process include the growth of the company's revenue, the minimization of financial risks or production costs, and the enhancement of operational efficiency. Drawing from the

experiences of foreign nations and the guidance provided by UNIDO, the assessment of investment project effectiveness is conducted based on two criteria: financial and economic evaluation. These criteria serve to complement one another in the evaluation process.

Financial evaluation focuses on analyzing liquidity throughout the investment project's execution. Essentially, the purpose of this assessment is to ascertain whether the enterprise possesses adequate financial resources to meet its total financial obligations and successfully implement the project within the designated timeframe. Conversely, economic evaluation aims to assess the investment project's potential to preserve the value of the funds allocated to it and to illustrate the anticipated growth of these funds at an acceptable level. The accompanying figure delineates the primary detection methods for each criterion and categorizes them accordingly.

In nations characterized by a developed market economy, it is customary to disseminate financial statements of businesses via mass media or in various compilations. Such collections provide access to information regarding the financial condition of companies. Globally, numerous methods have been established for evaluating the economic efficiency of investment projects, which can be broadly categorized into two main groups:

- **Simple (or statistical) assessment methods;**
- **valuation methods based on discounting.**

The first group includes:

- Payback Period, **PP**;
- Accounting Rate of Return, **ARR**.

The second group includes:

- Net Present Value, **NPV**;
- Internal Rate of Return, **IRR**;
- Profitability Index, **PI**;
- Discount Payback Period, **DPP**.

The approach to calculating the payback period for investments, in contrast to methods that utilize discounted cash flows, aims to identify the timeframe within which the initial investments can be recouped in nominal terms. This method fundamentally relies on assessing the duration required to recover the investment costs through the income generated from the execution of the investment project. More specifically, the payback period can be defined as the time it takes for the project to reach completion or the point at which the income generated equals the total amount invested.

The formula for calculating it is as follows: $PP = \frac{I_0}{CF_t}$

here, I_0 -initial investments; CF_t the amount of annual cash income received from the implementation of the investment project. It represents the net profit, or the difference between annual income and expenses (without depreciation).

The payback period of an investment project refers to the duration required for the returns generated by the project to recoup the initial costs incurred. The financial and economic assessment of any project relies heavily on data regarding cash flows. Without this information, it is not feasible to gauge the effectiveness of an investment project. Since the evaluation occurs prior to the project's execution, cash flow data must also be projected in advance. The planning and management of cash flows are crucial in assessing the project's effectiveness and significantly influence the determination of the actual viability of investment initiatives.

Methods for evaluating the effectiveness of investment projects through discounting can ascertain the profitability, efficiency, utility, and appeal of any investment endeavor. However, it may not always be necessary to apply all available methods in the evaluation process. The selection of these methods should consider the unique aspects and characteristics of each project being analyzed.

The techniques employed to assess the appeal of a project may not uncover all its characteristics; however, they are essential in establishing the project's true effectiveness.

Net present value (NPV) refers to the value derived from discounting all revenues and costs over a designated timeframe at a constant interest rate throughout the investment's duration. It signifies the difference between total inflows and outflows. The fundamental concept involves adjusting the annual net cash flow to reflect its value in the initial year of the project's execution for each period, ultimately resulting in a monetary figure known as net present value or net discounted income.

The formula for calculating it is as follows

$$NPV = \frac{CF_1}{(1+d)^1} + \frac{CF_2}{(1+d)^2} + \dots + \frac{CF_t}{(1+d)^t} - I_0$$

$$\text{or } NPV = \sum_{n=1}^t \frac{CF_t}{(1+d)^t} - I_0$$

here, NPV-net present value; d - discount rate; I_0 -initial investment; CF_t -cash flow received at the end of period t.

The discount rate criterion should align with the interest rate applicable to long-term loans in the capital market or the rate incurred by the borrower in practice. Essentially, this criterion serves as the minimum profitability threshold; any return

below this level is deemed ineffective for the investor. When evaluating investment projects using the net present value (NPV) method, a positive NPV ($NPV > 0$) indicates that the investment's profitability exceeds the discount rate. Conversely, if NPV equals zero, the project's profitability matches the discount rate, representing the minimum acceptable return. If NPV is negative ($NPV < 0$), it signifies that the project's profitability falls short of the minimum threshold.

In the initial two scenarios, the investment project is feasible. The first scenario suggests that the investor's capital will experience growth, whereas the second scenario indicates that there will be no change in capital, neither an increase nor a decrease. In the third scenario, it fails to yield the anticipated returns from the project. The net present value method serves solely to quantitatively illustrate the increase in the initial investment amount, reflecting the investor's wealth. However, relying solely on quantitative changes and outcomes is insufficient for assessing the efficiency of the investment.

When discussing the benefits of the net present value (NPV) method for evaluating the financial and economic viability of investment projects, it is essential to highlight its extensive application and popularity. This method is versatile, applicable under various conditions, and is likely to yield effective economic outcomes. However, it primarily addresses whether the investment project will contribute to the increase in the investor's wealth, and it may not serve as a wholly accurate criterion in certain situations:

-When selecting among various investment projects, if the net present values are equal, the magnitude of the investment costs—whether large or small—will not be considered;

-When choosing one of the investment projects, if the payback period of the project with a large net present value is long, and the payback period of the project with a small net present value is short, the net present value indicator is taken into account, without taking into account the payback period of the investment, and this indicator in which project is higher, this project is considered effective, which means that this method is not absolutely correct.

Advantages of using the net present value method include:

1. This metric signifies the anticipated returns from investments, illustrating the net cash flow generated by the project relative to the initial capital outlay.
2. It considers the duration of the investment project's viability and the temporal distribution of cash flows associated with the project.
3. The time element is incorporated and represented in present value terms.

4. The net present value (NPV) metric is cumulative over time, allowing for the aggregation of NPV figures from various projects.

5. It provides a predictive assessment of the potential changes in the economic capacity of the enterprise (firm, investor) resulting from the acceptance of the investment project for funding, specifically indicating the increase in the "wealth of the firm."

This method corresponds to the most basic criteria for evaluating the efficiency of investment projects.

Disadvantages of using the net present value method include:

1. NPV is an absolute indicator, it represents the difference between the discounted income and expenses of the project, but does not take into account the amount of income and expenses of alternative investment projects;

2. Since it is an absolute indicator, it does not represent the profitability of the project;

3. The discount rate depends on the value;

4. The discount rate is assumed to be constant during the entire duration of the project, but the discount rate may change later depending on the change in economic conditions;

5. It requires specific long-term indicators;

Therefore, it is necessary to use other methods of economic assessment to determine the relative growth of investments and the level of its growth.

Net present value rate (NPVR)

The net present value ratio is the ratio of the net present value to the total investment. Calculating the net present value of different items can compare their profitability. Its formula is:

$$NPVR = \frac{NPV}{I_p} * 100\%$$

NPVR represents the net present value rate and I_p -represents the present value of the investment.

When comparing the two schemes, the one with the higher NPVR is chosen, as a greater NPVR indicates a larger disparity between its value and the investment cost, thereby demonstrating its potential to generate higher net income.

Methods for assessing the effectiveness of investment projects through discounting can ascertain the profitability, efficiency, utility, and appeal of any given investment initiative. However, it may not always be necessary to apply all available

methods in the evaluation process. The selection of these methods should be tailored to the unique aspects and characteristics of each project being analyzed. While the methods used to evaluate a project's attractiveness may not capture every detail, they are essential in establishing the project's true effectiveness.

Conclusions

To enhance the level of investments in the national economy through domestic sources, the following measures should be implemented:

- enhancement of the current mechanisms within the national economy that facilitate the transformation of savings into investments;
- mobilization of financial resources held by the populace through commercial banks, whether in national or foreign currency, and offering these as loans to business entities;
- channeling funds accumulated by the public into the investment process via platforms such as the stock exchanges, among others.

The successful modernization and development of the national economy can be achieved through the formulation of effective investment projects within the country. The execution of these projects will not only facilitate the creation of additional activities and production but will also contribute to enhancing the well-being of the population and augmenting the state's wealth. Furthermore, it will strengthen the economic power of the nation, which is a true indicator of the quality of life within society. This approach is also a crucial element in addressing various socio-economic challenges faced by the economy.

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